

Original Research

Mycoprotein production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* through solid-state fermentation using soybean as a medium

Anita Rahmawati¹, Rina Sri Kasiamdari¹, Shin-Yee Fung², Boon-Hong Kong², Sari Darmasiwi^{1,*}

Abstract

Mycoprotein represents an alternative protein source that offers both nutritional and health benefits. This study aimed to evaluate the production of mycoprotein from *Lentinus squarrosulus* through solid-state fermentation (SSF) using soybeans as the substrate. Fermentation was carried out for 15 days at 23–25 °C on both the control (soybean only) and soybean fermented with *Lentinus squarrosulus*. Parameters measured included biomass yield, proximate composition, amino acid profile, and antioxidant activity. Results showed that the fungus successfully colonised the substrate on day 10 (32.35 ± 2.54 g), followed by a decline at day 15, indicating an optimal fermentation window before nutrient depletion. SSF resulted in increased moisture (11.37%), ash (5.74%), and carbohydrate content (28.16%), whereas protein decreased from 44.76% to 36.43% compared with the control. Essential amino acids, including threonine, leucine, and phenylalanine, were reduced after fermentation. The antioxidant activity decreased in the fermented sample, with an IC₅₀ of 32.05 ± 1.01 µg/mL, compared to 25.10 ± 0.91 µg/mL in the control. These findings demonstrate that soybean-based SSF supports the growth of *L. squarrosulus* and biomass formation; however, optimisation is required to enhance protein quality and preserve bioactive components. Overall, *L. squarrosulus* remains a promising yet underutilised candidate for sustainable mycoprotein development.

Keywords

Mycoprotein, *Lentinus squarrosulus*, Solid-state fermentation, proximate analysis, amino acids.

1 Department of Tropical Biology, Faculty of Biology, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta 52281, Indonesia

2 Department of Molecular Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur 50603 Malaysia

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: saridarma@ugm.ac.id

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Proizvodnja mikoproteinov iz *Lentinus squarrosulus* s fermentacijo v trdnem stanju z uporabo soje kot medija

Izvleček

Mikoprotein predstavlja alternativni vir beljakovin, ki ponuja tako prehranske kot zdravstvene koristi. Namen te študije je bil oceniti proizvodnjo mikoproteina iz *Lentinus squarrosulus* s pomočjo fermentacije v trdnem stanju (SSF) z uporabo soje kot substrata. Fermentacija je potekala 15 dni pri temperaturi 23–25 °C tako za kontrolne vzorce (samo soja) kot na soji fermentirani z *Lentinus squarrosulus*. Merjeni parametri so vključevali prirast biomase, sestavo, profil aminokislin in antioksidativno aktivnost. Rezultati so pokazali, da je gliva uspešno prerastla substrat 10. dan po nanosu ($32,35 \pm 2,54$ g), čemur je 15. Dan sledil upad, kar kaže na optimalno obdobje fermentacije pred izčrpanjem hranil. SSF je povzročila povečanje vlage (11,37 %), pepela (5,74 %) in vsebnosti ogljikovih hidratov (28,16 %), medtem ko se je vsebnost beljakovin v primerjavi s kontrolno skupino zmanjšala s 44,76 % na 36,43 %. Po fermentaciji se je zmanjšala vsebnost esencialnih aminokislin, vključno s treoninom, levcinom in fenilalaninom. Antioksidativna aktivnost se je v fermentiranem vzorcu zmanjšala, z IC_{50} $32,05 \pm 1,01$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$ v primerjavi z $25,10 \pm 0,91$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$ v kontrolni skupini. Ti rezultati kažejo, da SSF na osnovi soje podpira rast *L. squarrosulus* in prirast biomase, vendar je potrebna optimizacija za izboljšanje kakovosti beljakovin in ohranitev bioaktivnih sestavin. Na splošno ostaja *L. squarrosulus* obetaven, a premalo izkoriščen kandidat za trajnostni razvoj mikoproteinov.

Ključne besede

Mikoprotein, *Lentinus squarrosulus*, fermentacija v trdnem stanju, imediatna analiza, aminokislina.

Introduction

Global demand for alternative protein sources will increase along with an increase in population and the need for sustainable food systems. Thus, it certainly requires alternative proteins that can support nutrition and have high nutritional value. Mycoprotein refers to proteins derived from fungi (yeast or filamentous fungi) in biomass. It can be used as an alternative protein that has nutritional components such as protein, amino acids, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals. Mycoprotein is produced from fungal mycelium, which not only provides an alternative protein source but also allows for value addition to the substrate through solid-state fermentation (SSF) (Stoffel et al., 2019). Mycoprotein is a whole-food source that is produced sustainably and rich in protein. Consumption of mycoprotein may help reduce circulating cholesterol levels by around 21%, supported by its beneficial amino acid profile and its dietary fibre content, mainly consisting of β -glucan and chitin, which can affect the gut microbiota to produce a cholesterol-lowering effect (Coelho et al., 2020).

Solid-state fermentation is increasingly used in

industrial and pharmaceutical fields because it employs substrates with minimal liquid content. It is a continuous, low-water bioprocess in which microorganisms, particularly filamentous fungi, grow on moist substrates without free water, producing hydrolytic enzymes such as cellulases, hemicellulases, and lignin-degrading enzymes that convert agricultural residues into value-added metabolites and bioactive compounds with enhanced bioactivity (Wu et al., 2013). Mycoproteins produced through this process have a Protein Digestibility-Corrected Amino Acid Score (PDCAAS) that is higher than that of chicken and beef protein (Majumder et al., 2023). After the fermentation period, fungal biomass is harvested, and extraction from non-edible substrates may involve organic solvents such as hexane (Majumder et al., 2023). The selection of microorganisms plays a key role in SSF because it affects the productivity, efficiency, and quality of fermentation outcomes (Wang et al., 2023). The resulting mycoproteins have a Protein Digestibility-Corrected Amino Acid Score (PDCAAS) that is higher than that of chicken and beef protein (Majumder et al., 2023).

Lentinus squarrosulus is an edible mushroom with high

nutritional value (Ugbogu et al., 2024). Proteins from the genus *Lentinus*, including *L. squarrosulus* and *L. edodes*, play an effective role in suppressing free radical reactions into harmless substances, exhibiting antioxidant activity. *L. squarrosulus* can even be used as a treatment, such as lowering blood pressure and cholesterol levels (Kriangkrai et al., 2024). In addition, components of *L. squarrosulus*, particularly its proteins and polysaccharides, showed antitumor and immunomodulatory effects (Lau & Abdullah, 2017) and hold potential for pharmaceutical applications, including cardioprotective applications (Rosa et al., 2013). However, despite these promising attributes, *L. squarrosulus* remains underexplored compared to widely studied genera such as *Pleurotus*, *Agaricus*, *Agrocybe*, and *Lentinula*. Most existing studies emphasise *L. squarrosulus* bioactive compounds, whereas research on its potential as a mycoprotein-producing fungus, especially under SSF, is extremely limited. Recent reports highlight its relatively high protein content, including all the essential amino acids, β -glucan, and being low in fat, and are recommended as a nutritional supplement for patients with cardiac problems, suggesting that *L. squarrosulus* is a promising yet underutilised candidate for sustainable fungal protein development (Ugbogu et al., 2024; Bakratsas et al., 2023). This lack of SSF-based mycoprotein research represents a clear and important knowledge gap.

Soybean is often chosen as a substrate in fermentation for mycoprotein production because they is rich in protein and carbohydrates, which provide essential nitrogen and carbon sources for fungal growth. Studies have shown that soy-based substrates like soy whey support the growth of fungi used in mycoprotein production, such as *Aspergillus oryzae*, leading to high biomass and protein yields under optimised conditions (Pratama et al., 2025). The composition and availability of nutrients in soybean products make them ideal for sustainable and efficient fungal cultivation in both submerged and solid-state fermentation processes.

This study aims to examine the potential of *Lentinus squarrosulus* for mycoprotein production through solid-state fermentation on soybean, focusing on biomass yield, proximate composition, and amino acid profile to assess its nutritional quality. Addressing this gap will provide foundational data to support the development of a new, sustainable, and high-value fungi-derived protein source. These findings are expected to advance the utilisation of fungal mycelia as practical and environmentally sustainable alternative proteins.

Materials and Methods

Inoculating *Lentinus squarrosulus* on PDA medium

Fresh basidiomes of mushrooms were obtained from the forest surrounding the village of Suak Gual, Belitung, Indonesia (2°54'49 "S 107°23'13" E), and were placed in clean zip-lock bags, sun-dried, transported, and subsequently stored at 4 °C until laboratory processing. The material was later identified as *Lentinus squarrosulus* based on morphological characteristics and molecular analysis. Prior to isolation, the basidiomes were rinsed under running water to remove surface debris and cut into smaller fragments. Tissue fragments were briefly immersed in a dilute sodium hypochlorite solution (10%) to reduce surface contaminants, followed by thorough rinsing with sterile distilled water. The partially dried tissues were transferred onto potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates and incubated at 25 ± 2 °C for 15-20 days to allow the emergence of fungal mycelia (Maysaroh et al., 2025). An inoculum block of 1 cm² from the active growing culture was transferred aseptically onto a Petri dish containing 20 mL of sterile PDA medium and then incubated at 28 °C for 15 to 20 days until complete colonisation on PDA medium (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Preparation of fermentation substrate

The fermentation substrate was prepared from soybeans hydrated in a 1:3 ratio. Specifically, a total of 20 g of whole soybeans were mixed with 60 mL of distilled water, and allowed to hydrate, after which the hydrated soybeans and soaking liquid were transferred into a 250-mL Erlenmeyer flask and sterilised using an autoclave at 121 °C, 15 min, 1 atm to soften the substrate and ensure microbial decontamination (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Biomass production

Sterile hydrated soybean substrate was inoculated using 5% (w/w) actively growing mycelial agar plugs of *L. squarrosulus*. The flasks were covered with cotton plugs and incubated at 24-28 °C for two weeks. The colonisation process was observed every day, with samples taken on days 0, 5, 10, and 15, each with three replications for each treatment for a total of 12 flasks. After full colonisation was achieved, the soybean substrate and mycelium were oven-dried at 60 °C

for 24 h under controlled relative humidity (40–45%), then ground using a blender at 10000 rpm for 10 min. Biomass was measured by weighing the dry weight before and after cultivation. Biomass yield was calculated as grams of dry biomass per gram of initial dry substrate (g/g dry substrate), using the formula: (dry biomass – initial substrate weight) / initial substrate weight (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Proximate analysis

Proximate composition is evaluated by proximal composition analysis. The compositions analysed are moisture, ash, fat, protein, and carbohydrates, following the AOAC standard. Moisture was analysed using the Gravimetric method, which involves drying samples at 100–105 °C until they reach a constant weight. Ash analysis using incineration at 550 °C. Fat analysis was measured using Soxhlet extraction, and protein analysis was determined using the Kjeldahl method (AOAC, 2005).

Amino acid analysis

Amino acid analysis of mushroom-derived mycoprotein generally involves two main steps. First, amino acids are released from the biomass by hydrolysis of the samples with 6 M HCl at 110 °C for 24 h to break the proteins into free amino acids. After hydrolysis, the amino acids are derivatised with NAD (naphthalene-2,3-dicarboxaldehyde) at pH 9, and subsequently identified and quantified using a High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) system (Biotech HPLC model 525, Hallertau, Germany) equipped with an LIF detector from a capillary electrophoresis system (model PNA8C) as described by Rodrigues et al. (2018). Chromatographic separation is performed on a Supercosil LC-18-DB reversed-phase column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm; Supelco Analytical, Bellefonte, USA) at 40 °C with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The mobile phase consists of water acidified with trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) at pH 2 (mobile phase A) and acetonitrile (mobile phase B) (Stoffel et al., 2019).

Antioxidant analysis

Antioxidant activity was measured using the DPPH radical scavenging activity (RSA) assay. The extract was prepared by performing aqueous extraction on dried mushroom mycelia. The extraction was carried out by stirring the mycelial material in sterile distilled water (1:10), centrifuging

at 3,500 × g for 10 min, and the resulting supernatant was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrate was then freeze-dried. The dried extract was subsequently dissolved in sterile distilled water to prepare solutions containing 30–30000 µg/mL of extract. A total of 30 µL of ethanolic extracts at different concentrations were added to a 96-well microplate containing 170 µL of DPPH reagent in methanol (6 × 10⁻⁵ mol/L) and incubated in the dark for 30 min. Absorbance was measured at 517 nm (Multiskan, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) using DPPH in methanol as a negative control and ascorbic acid as a positive control. The antioxidant radical scavenging activity of DPPH was calculated using the following equation: % Radical Scavenging Activity (RSA) = [(A control - A sample) / A control] × 100. The reduction in absorbance caused by the test samples was evaluated relative to the positive control. Ascorbic acid served as the reference antioxidant and was used as the positive control. The concentration of extract required to achieve 50% free radical scavenging (IC₅₀) was determined by plotting the percentage of radical scavenging activity (RSA) against the extract concentration and calculating the value from the resulting curve (Heleno et al., 2015).

Data analysis

Data were measured in triplicate, analysed for mean and standard deviation, followed by one-way ANOVA and post hoc test using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT), with significance set at p < 0.05. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25.

Results

Biomass production

Biomass production from solid-state fermentation was evaluated using *Lentinus squarrosulus* grown on a soybean substrate. The fungal inoculation aimed to enhance biomass yield compared to the uninoculated control (Figure 1). Figure 1a shows the soybean substrate before fermentation, where the beans appear clean, hydrated, and uninoculated, with no visible fungal growth. Figure 1b shows the substrate after solid-state fermentation with *Lentinus squarrosulus*, displaying dense white mycelial growth covering the surface and filling the spaces between the soybean pieces, indicating successful colonisation and active substrate utilisation.

The morphological changes shown in Figure 1, marked by dense mycelial growth on the substrate, are supported by the biomass production, which quantifies the increase in total biomass over the course of fermentation. Biomass production was determined by comparing the initial substrate weight with the final weight after fermentation. The results of biomass production at days 5, 10, and 15 are presented in Table 1.

The biomass production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* during solid-state fermentation (SSF) varied throughout the incubation period (Table 1). On day 5, biomass reached 32.28 ± 0.10 g, followed by a slight increase to 32.35 ± 2.54 g on day 10. By day 15, biomass decreased to 26.72 ± 1.73 g. The uninoculated substrate exhibited a dry mass of 15.05 g, which serves as the baseline for accurately quantifying biomass accumulation attributable to fungal growth. These results indicate that the highest biomass production occurred within the first 10 days of fermentation, after which growth declined, likely due to nutrient depletion or accumulation of inhibitory metabolites. Identifying this optimal fermentation period is important to ensure efficient

fungal growth and maximise the performance of the SSF process for downstream applications.

Proximate composition

Proximate analysis was conducted to determine the effect of solid-state fermentation (SSF) with *Lentinus squarrosulus* on the nutrient composition of the soybean substrate. The analysis compared the unfermented control with the fermented sample, focusing on standard proximate parameters: moisture, ash, fat, protein, and carbohydrate content. The results, expressed as percentage values to facilitate clearer nutritional comparison, are presented in Table 2.

The proximate composition of the fermented product exhibited distinct changes compared to the control (Table 2). Moisture content increased from $9.10 \pm 0.05\%$ in the control (uninoculated soybean) to $11.37 \pm 0.11\%$ following SSF with *L. squarrosulus*. Ash content also rose from $4.62 \pm 0.05\%$ to $5.74 \pm 0.25\%$, indicating mineral enrichment during fermentation. Fat content remained unchanged at 17.26% in both treatments. In contrast, protein content

Figure 1. Visual comparison of (a) soybean substrate before and (b) after solid-state fermentation using *Lentinus squarrosulus*.

Slika 1. Vizualna primerjava (a) sojinlega substrata pred in (b) po fermentaciji v trdnem stanju z uporabo *Lentinus squarrosulus*.

Table 1. Biomass production of *Lentinus squarrosulus* during SSF on soybean medium.

Tabela 1. Proizvodnja biomase *Lentinus squarrosulus* med SSF na sojinah medijih

Incubation time (days)	Biomass (g)
Day 5	$32.28 \pm 0.10a$
Day 10	$32.35 \pm 2.54a$
Day 15	$26.72 \pm 1.73b$

*Different superscript letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$.

decreased from $44.76 \pm 0.33\%$ in the control to $36.43 \pm 0.06\%$ in the fermented sample, whereas carbohydrate content increased from $24.26 \pm 0.47\%$ to $28.16 \pm 0.71\%$. These compositional shifts suggest that SSF with *L. squarrosulus* modifies the nutritional profile of the substrate, likely through fungal metabolic activities and enzymatic degradation of macromolecules that reduce protein while enhancing ash and carbohydrate fractions.

Amino acid profile

Amino acid content analysis was carried out to determine the nutritional value of the fermentation results by comparing the Control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*, focusing on both essential and non-essential amino acids.

Table 2. Proximate composition of uninoculated soybean (control) and soybean fermented by *Lentinus squarrosulus* under solid-state fermentation (SSF).

Tabela 2. Približna sestava neinokulirane soje (kontrola) in soje, fermentirane z *Lentinus squarrosulus* v trdnem stanju (SSF).

Composition	Control (Uninoculated Soybean)	SSF with <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i>
Moisture (%)	$9.10 \pm 0.05a$	$11.37 \pm 0.11b$
Ash (%)	$4.62 \pm 0.05a$	$5.74 \pm 0.25ab$
Fat (%)	$17.26 \pm 0.69a$	$17.26 \pm 0.63ab$
Protein (%)	$44.76 \pm 0.33b$	$36.43 \pm 0.06a$
Carbohydrates (%)	$24.26 \pm 0.47a$	$28.16 \pm 0.71b$

*Different superscript letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Comparative essential amino acid composition in control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$. ns = non-significant.

Slika 2. Primerjava sestave esencialnih aminokislin v kontrolni skupini (neokupljena soja) in SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Različne črke označujejo statistično pomembne razlike pri $p < 0,05$. ns = nepomembno.

Table 3. Value of amino acid composition in control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*.Tabela 3. Vrednost sestave aminokislin v kontrolni skupini (neinokulirana soja) in SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*.

Essential amino acid	Control (uninoculated soybeans) (%)	SSF <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i> (%)	Non-essential amino acid	Control (uninoculated soybeans) (%)	SSF <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i> (%)
Isoleucine	0.079±0	0.074±0.001	L-Aspartic acid	0.355±0.003	0.508±0.001
Leucine	0.259±0.005	0.179±0.001	L-Glutamic acid	0.625±0.004	0.688±0.003
Valine	0.062±0	0.053±0.001	L-Asparagine	0	0
Histidine	0.118±0.002	0.095±0.001	L-Histidine	0.095±0.001	0.118±0.002
Lysine	0.231±0.003	0.196±0.003	L-Serine	0.143±0.001	0.225±0
Methionine	0.095±0.001	0.052±0	L-Glutamine	0	0
Phenylalanine	0.167±0	0.141±0.001	L-Threonine	0.258±0.001	0.296±0.006
Threonine	0.296±0.006	0.258±0.001	L-Glycine	0.140±0.001	0.21±0
Tryptophan	0.112±0.004	0.026±0.003	L-Arginine	0.084±0.001	0.1145±0.001
			L-Alanine + L-Tyrosine	0.122±0.001	0.195±0

The essential amino acid profile of soybean after solid-state fermentation (SSF) with *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed clear shifts compared to the uninoculated control, as presented in Figure 2. In the control sample, threonine (0.30%), leucine (0.26%), lysine (~0.24%), phenylalanine (~0.17%), and histidine (~0.12%) were present at the highest concentrations, marking them as the dominant essential amino acids. After fermentation, the levels of these amino acids decreased to approximately 0.26% for threonine, 0.18% for leucine, 0.20% for lysine, 0.14% for phenylalanine, and 0.09% for histidine, indicating a general reduction across most essential amino acid categories. Valine also declined slightly from about 0.06% to 0.05%, while methionine showed a more pronounced decrease, dropping from around 0.10% in the control to roughly 0.05% in the SSF sample. In contrast, isoleucine displayed a modest improvement following fermentation, increasing slightly from ~0.08% to ~0.09–0.10%. Tryptophan experienced the most substantial decline, falling sharply from approximately 0.12% in the control to about 0.03% in the fermented product. These patterns collectively demonstrate that SSF with *L. squarrosulus* alters the essential amino acid composition of soybean, largely reducing most amino acids while slightly enhancing isoleucine content.

The non-essential amino acid content of mycoprotein produced through SSF by *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed clear differences compared to the control. Based on Figure

3, glutamic acid and aspartic acid remained the two most abundant non-essential amino acids in both samples; however, both decreased after fermentation.

Glutamic acid declined markedly from 0.70% in the control to approximately 0.55% in the SSF product, while aspartic acid dropped from about 0.50% to 0.30%. Asparagine also decreased from roughly 0.65% to 0.55%. Serine, glutamine, glycine, arginine, and the combined value of alanine + tyrosine each showed significant reductions after SSF, as indicated by different letter groupings in the graph. In contrast, alanine remained relatively stable between the two treatments (around 0.14%). Overall, SSF with *Lentinus squarrosulus* resulted in a general decline in most non-essential amino acids, likely due to their utilisation for fungal growth or enzymatic metabolism during fermentation (Imelda et al., 2008).

Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity was evaluated by comparing the fermented substrate with the control using the DPPH radical scavenging assay. The results are presented in Table 4, including the percentage of DPPH radical scavenging activity and IC₅₀ values.

The antioxidant activity of the samples showed that the control exhibited the highest DPPH radical scavenging activity at 64,445 ± 3997,63%, followed by *Lentinus squar-*

Figure 3. Comparative Essential Amino Acid Composition in Control (uninoculated soybeans) and SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$. ns = non-significant.

Slika 3. Primerjava sestave esencialnih aminokislin v kontrolni skupini (neokupljena soja) in SSF *Lentinus squarrosulus*. *Različne črke označujejo statistično pomembne razlike pri $p < 0,05$. ns = statistično nepomembno

Table 4. Antioxidant activity of uninoculated soybean (control) and soybean fermented by *Lentinus squarrosulus* under solid-state fermentation (SSF).

Tabela 4. Antioksidativna aktivnost neokužene soje (kontrola) in soje, fermentirane z *Lentinus squarrosulus* v trdnem stanju (SSF).

Sample	% DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)
Control	64,445.65 ± 3,997.63a	25.10 ± 0.91a
SSF with <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i>	49,545.90 ± 3,870.56b	32.05 ± 1.01b
Vitamin C		8.78

*Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$. ns = non-significant

rosulus with $49,545 \pm 3870,56$ %. As expected, vitamin C demonstrated the strongest antioxidant potency as the positive control. Based on IC₅₀ values, vitamin C had the lowest IC₅₀ (8.78 µg/mL), indicating high radical scavenging effectiveness. The control sample recorded an IC₅₀ of 25.10 ± 0.91 µg/mL, while *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed a higher IC₅₀ of 32.05 ± 1.01 µg/mL, suggesting reduced antioxidant capacity after fermentation. These results imply that although *Lentinus squarrosulus* retained antioxidant activity, fermentation may have decreased its overall capacity compared to the non-fermented control.

Discussion

Based on the results, there was a significant difference in biomass production between the fermented treatment and the control. In this study, biomass refers to the total dry weight of the fermented substrate (mycelium and residual substrate combined). The increase in biomass production in fermentation treatment using fungal isolate can be related to the ability of white rot fungi, including *Lentinus squarrosulus*, to increase the nutritional value or nutritional quality of the fermentation substrate (Wang et al., 2024).

This is in line with the research of Pascual et al. (2025), which states that SSF uses edible mushrooms to utilise biological substrates as a source of nutrients to support growth and biomass production. Soybeans, as a substrate rich in protein and carbohydrates, provide optimal sources of nitrogen and carbon to support mycelial growth and biomass production. Soybeans have pharmacological properties against heart disease, cancer, and osteoporosis (Lee et al., 2019).

In general, the results of solid-state fermentation (SSF) using the fungus *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed changes in most parameters compared to the control. Overall, the proximate composition showed the highest value in fermentation. The fermented samples exhibited higher moisture (11.37%), ash (9.10%), and carbohydrate contents (28.16%) than the control, while protein content decreased relative to unfermented soybeans. These shifts are directly linked to the metabolic activity of *L. squarrosulus* during SSF. Moisture increases arise from metabolic water produced during fungal respiration and from the ability of fungal mycelia to retain water via dense hyphal networks; this retained moisture enhances the mobility and diffusion of extracellular enzymes, thereby promoting substrate hydrolysis and fungal growth during solid-state fermentation (SSF) (Lizardi-Jimenez et al., 2015). Ash content reflects the total mineral accumulation by the fungus, which varies due to growth conditions and rates (Ahmed et al., 2015). The increased carbohydrate levels during fermentation with *Lentinus squarrosulus* are thought to be related to the activity of hydrolytic enzymes produced during mycelial growth. Carbohydrates in soybeans (such as pectin, hemicellulose, and cellulose) can be broken down into simpler forms by a combination of enzymes (pectinase, xylanase, cellulase, α -galactosidase). In addition, proteases also play a role in increasing the access of carbohydrate enzymes to the substrate by breaking down barrier proteins. Proteases help enhance the accessibility of these carbohydrate-degrading enzymes by breaking down structural or barrier proteins within the substrate. This continuous hydrolysis increases carbohydrate availability, which is reflected in the rising carbohydrate levels. The synergy between proteases and carbohydrate-hydrolysing enzymes is therefore an important factor contributing to this increase (Loman & Ju, 2017).

Despite the metabolic activity and visible increase in fungal biomass, protein content decreased during solid-state fermentation because *Lentinus squarrosulus* uti-

lises soybean proteins as its primary nitrogen and energy sources (Lau & Abdullah, 2017). Fungal biomass formation does not necessarily increase measurable crude protein in the substrate, as many liberated amino acids are catabolized for energy or incorporated into fungal structures not fully quantified by standard proximate analysis. Conversely, the decrease in protein levels during fermentation with *Lentinus squarrosulus* is likely due to high protease activity, which is capable of hydrolysing protein and subsequently reducing their levels. The extent of protein degradation depends on enzyme specificity, as different proteases can exhibit varying levels of effectiveness even when acting on the same substrate. This suggests that the enzymatic profile of fungi plays an important role in determining the final composition of fermentation products (Fang et al., 2022). It was also supported by research from Deng et al. (2025) that reviewed the synergistic roles of proteases, α -amylases, and carbohydrases in degrading proteins and starches during fermentation, increasing nutrient utilisation efficiency.

Essential amino acids in the fermentation of soybeans using *Lentinus squarrosulus* showed lower levels compared to the control. Although all essential amino acids decreased, tryptophan (0.03 %) and methionine (0.05 %) showed the most significant reductions. According to Lata & Atri (2017), within the genus *Lentinus*, methionine is recorded at the lowest level among the essential amino acids, and it plays important roles in fat metabolism and antioxidant activity. Likewise, Afiukwa et al. (2015) reported that tryptophan in the genus *Lentinus* is often not detected due to its very low levels. However, in *Lentinus squarrosulus*, threonine levels (0.26 %) showed the highest among the essential amino acid levels, even though the overall essential amino acid levels remained lower than the control, in accordance with Afiukwa et al. (2015), who noted that threonine is the most abundant essential amino acid in the genus *Lentinus*. Most non-essential amino acids in the fermentation of *Lentinus squarrosulus* also showed reduced levels compared to the control. The most significant decrease was observed in tyrosine, which was also found in several *Lentinus* species but typically at lower levels than other non-essential amino acids, as reported by Lata & Atri (2017). The decrease in amino acid levels in *Lentinus squarrosulus* is most likely due to overfermentation. This indicates that fermentation duration plays an important role, as excessively long fermentation can disrupt protein accumulation or lead to protein degradation (Vahidi et al., 2017). Critically, the

fermentation duration strongly influenced amino acid degradation. Longer SSF periods may promote overfermentation, during which amino acids are deaminated, oxidised, or metabolised as secondary energy sources, resulting in substantial losses. This mechanism aligns with Çabuk et al. (2018, who noted that longer fermentation can reduce sulfur amino acid (like methionine) scores.

Fermented samples (IC_{50} : 32.05 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) showed lower antioxidant capacity than the control (25.10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), since higher IC_{50} values indicate weaker DPPH radical scavenging. This reduction is consistent with the decreased levels of certain amino acids, particularly aromatic ones, that contribute to antioxidant capability. In addition to amino acid changes, fermentation may also affect other bioactive constituents such as phenolics, flavonoids, polysaccharides, and small antioxidant molecules (e.g., ergothioneine and glutathione). These compounds are often metabolised or structurally modified during fungal growth, and their reduction or transformation can further contribute to the weakened antioxidant activity. According to Liu et al. (2020), lower IC_{50} values correspond to greater free radical scavenging potential, so the higher IC_{50} observed here clearly reflects a reduction in antioxidant potency. Nevertheless, reported IC_{50} values for *Lentinus squarrosulus* extracts (26–65 $\mu\text{g/mL}$; Fabros et al., 2022) suggest that the species retains meaningful functional potential despite these biochemical changes.

Overall, the proximate and amino acid shifts observed here—together with alterations in non-protein antioxidant metabolites—reflect not only the enzymatic activities of *L. squarrosulus* but also the influence of fermentation duration, substrate utilisation patterns, and metabolic priorities of the fungus. These interpretations offer a more mechanistic understanding of how SSF modifies soybean composition and functional properties, beyond simply restating the results.

Conclusions

Solid-state fermentation using *Lentinus squarrosulus* on the soybean medium has been shown to increase biomass production compared to the control, which is soybean medium without fungal inoculation, indicating that the fungus can grow well on soybean substrate. The fermentation process also affects the nutritional composition, with an increase in water, ash, and carbohydrate content.

However, the levels of protein and essential amino acids decreased compared to the control. In addition, *Lentinus squarrosulus* also exhibits significant antioxidant activity. This shows that although *Lentinus squarrosulus* has the potential to produce mycoprotein, further optimisation is needed to improve the quality of its protein, especially regarding essential amino acid content. Future work may focus on optimising fermentation time with less than 10 days of fermentation, testing alternative substrates such as wheat bran to improve amino-acid retention, and evaluating another strain of mushrooms with higher biomass yield and lower protease activity, as a potential alternative to enhance protein quality.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation and methodology, S.D.; analysis and research, A.R.; writing—original draft preparation, A,R and S.D.; writing—review and editing, R.S.K, S.Y.F, B.H.K.; supervision, S.D. and R.S.K; funding acquisition, S.D. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

Research data was deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17862445>)

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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